

TONE BEHAVIOUR IN YORÙBÁ VOWEL COALESCENCE: AN AUTOSEGMENTAL APPROACH

NAFISAT BOLANLE AIYELABEGAN¹

Department of Linguistics and Nigerian Languages,
Kwara State University, Malete

Phone No: +2348137232696

Email: nafisat.aiyelabegan@kwasu.edu.ng

TELLA SAMSON ADEKUNLE²

Department of Linguistics and Nigerian Languages,
Kwara State University, Malete

E-mail: samson.tella@kwasu.edu.ng / sttesam@gmail.com
07061259306

RIDWAN AKINKUNMI RABIU³

Department of Linguistics and Nigerian Languages,
Kwara State University, Malete

Email: ridwan.rabiu@kwasu.edu.ng

Phone Number: +2349060070668

Abstract

This paper examined the status of tone in Yoruba vowel coalescence. This is borne out of previous researches that have been carried out on the status of tone in other phonological processes in the Yorùbá language. The theoretical framework adopted for tone in Yoruba vowel coalescence is Autosegmental phonology propounded by Goldsmith in 1976. This theory sees tone as an independent segment. The data for this research work were sourced from existing literature such as Awobuluyi (1992), Oyebade (2008) Owolabi (2019), etc. We observed that tone in Yoruba vowel coalescence is stable and uninfluenced by the phonological process of vowel coalescence. Some of the modifications that tone in Yoruba vowel coalescence go through include tone assimilation, tone deletion, tone displacement through the process of delinking and relinking as well as tone coalescence. We observed that assimilation of tone in vowel coalescence does not conform to tone prominence. Also, tone deletion usually occurs when mid tones occur on the two coalesced vowels. It was observed that delinking and relinking of tone, which usually result in high rising contour tone in the Yorùbá language only occur in H+L+H that is High tone+ Low tone+ High tone context. In conclusion, our research into the status

of tone in Yoruba vowel coalescence has shown that tone is an independent segment in Yoruba vowel coalescence.

Keywords: Tone, Tone-Stability, Tone-Deletion, Tone-Displacement, Tone-Assimilation and Tone-Coalescence

Introduction

As it is in other tone languages, tone is highly phonemic in Yoruba. This is evident in the productivity of tone in the distributions of different phonological processes during interaction, and the unique role it plays in both syntactic and phonological interface.

The relationship between tone and vowels in Yoruba phonological processes have been examined by different scholars, most especially after the development of Autosegmental phonology which was propounded by Goldsmith in 1976. Some of the phonological processes in which the status of tone has been examined include vowel elision and vowel assimilation. Oyebade (2008, p.147) examines the status of tone in the Yorùbá language in vowel elision and assimilation. In his work, he asserts that tone is an independent segment in Yorùbá language. He explains that:

The first or second of two vowels could disappear as a result of an elision process but the tone of such survives to show up on the surviving vowel...The second vowel in a sequence totally assimilates all of the properties of the preceding vowel but the tone is impervious to this assimilation. This seems to be an evidence that tone and vowel segments are not contained in the same bundle.

Akinlabi (2016, p. 204) also examines the status of tone in Yoruba vowel assimilation and elision, he opines that “The stability of tone in the process of vowel assimilation and vowel deletion is of crucial importance. When a vowel gets assimilated or deleted, its tone remains behind on the surviving vowel except when it is a mid-tone”. Also Owolabi (2019) in his work explained the independence of tone in sound modification when he asserts that tonal assimilation in some instances occurs without vowel assimilation in Yoruba language. He gave the following examples to buttress his claim:

- | | | | | | |
|-------------------|--------|------------|--------------------------|-----------|-----------|
| 1i. Ọ̀wọ́ + ọ̀wọ́ | —————→ | ọ̀wọ̀ọ̀wọ́ | ‘row by row’ | row | row |
| ii. Ọ́jọ́ + ọ́jọ́ | —————→ | ọ́jọ̀ọ́jọ́ | ‘day by day’ | day | day |
| iii. Ẹgbé + ẹgbé | —————→ | ẹgbẹ̀ẹgbé | ‘associate by associate’ | | |
| | | | | associate | associate |

iv. Ègbé + ègbé —————> ègbèègbé ‘side by side’ side side

Vowel coalescence, which is the focus of this paper can be defined as the phonological process that occurs when two distinct vowels merge to generate a third distinct vowel has been well studied in the Yorùbá language by scholars such as Crowther (1852), Bouche (1885), de Gaye and Beecroft (1922), Abraham (1958), Awobuluyi (1964, 1989, 1992), Bamisile (1986, 1994) and Babarinde (2013) etc. but to the best of the researchers knowledge, little or no work that we know of has been carried out on the status of tone in Yorùbá vowel coalescence. In answer to this, this work seeks to fill this gap by examining the behaviour of tone when vowel coalescence occurs in the Yorùbá language. This work aims to examine the prosodic behaviour in the context of vowel coalescence in Yorùbá language in a bid to identify and state the unique derivational occurrence of tone in vowel coalescence in the Yorùbá language, it explains the prosodic steps through which the tonal behaviour in vowel coalescence are realised and illustrate the theoretical relevance in autosegmental phonology to this research.

Literature Review

Coalescence is a phonological process where the first vowel and the second vowel metamorphose into a new third vowel that is distinct from the two pre-existing vowels. The phonological schema for this process is $V_1 + V_2 \rightarrow V_3$. Bamgbose (1990, p.65) also explains that “vowel coalescence is a combination of two contiguous (underlying) vowels whose output is a different vowel entirely”. In addition, Babarinde (2013, p. 84) also defines coalescence as “a phonological process where two segments merge together to produce an entirely new segment distinct from the input... it is a term used in linguistics to refer to the coming together of linguistic units which are originally distinguishable”. Further-more, Ajiboye (2020, p.118) also defined coalescence as “a phonological process which allows two segments in the base to appear as one in the surface through a process popularly known as merging”. Awobuluyi (1992) in Ajiboye (2020, p.119) classified coalescence into three types, which are (i) coalescence by merger, (ii) coalescence by assimilation and (iii) coalescence by polarization which are attested in the Yoruba and Afa languages.

Some of the scholars that have researched into vowel coalescence in the Yoruba language are Crowther (1852), Bouche (1885), de Gaye and Beecroft (1922), Abraham (1958), Awobuluyi (1964, 1989, 1992), Bamgbose (1986, 1990), Bamisile (1986, 1994) and Babarinde (2013), Rabiú (2021), etc. Bamgbose (1990, p.65) in his work explains that vowel coalescence in the Yoruba language can be represented with this formula $V_1 + V_2 \rightarrow V_3$. Awobuluyi (1986) was the first to classify vowel coalescence in the Yoruba language into different classes. He classified Yoruba vowel coalescence into three main groups which are vowel

coalescence by merger, vowel coalescence by assimilation and vowel coalescence by polarization. Awobuluyi (1992) used examples from Yoruba verb phrase, i.e. verb + noun, noun phrase (noun + noun), numerals and nominalization through interfixation to buttress his claim on the presence of vowel coalescence in the Yoruba language. Bamisile (1986, 1994) also examined the presence of vowel coalescence in Èkìtì and Mòbà dialects of Yorùbá.

According to Olawuwo (2021), Awóbùlúyì (1972) observes that vowel coalescence in Yorùbá is accepted as involving two different vowels giving rise to a third vowel. So many scholars such as Bergeman (1971), Welmers (1973), Awóbùlúyì (1972) observe that vowel coalescence in Yorùbá patterns appropriately with its description cross-linguistically. Bamgbose (1990) establishes that:

Gégé bi a ti şàkiyèsí nípa fáwèlì pipajẹ, tí fáwèlì méjì bá fẹgbékẹgbẹ, òkàn nínú wọn ni a ó pa jẹ. Fáwèlì tó borí gbódò jẹ òkàn nínú àwọn fáèlì méjì àkókó. Nínú àwọn èhun Yorùbá kan ó dà bí ẹni pé èyí kó rí bẹẹ nítórí pé àbájáde fáwèlì pipajẹ máa n fún wa ni fáwèlì tí ó yàtò sí àwọn fáwèlì mejì àkókó.

(As we observed in vowel deletion, if two vowels appear near each other, one out of the two will be deleted. The winning vowel must be one out of the two initial vowels. In one of the structures of Yorùbá, it seems that this is not applicable because the output vowel deletion used to produce a vowel that is different from the two initial vowels).

Rabiu (2021) in his work also examined vowel coalescence in selected Yoruba places and personal names. All of the aforementioned scholars have analyzed vowel coalescence from phonological perspectives using data from Yorùbá numeral, derived nouns through the morphological process of compounding and affixation, place and personal names in Yoruba but to the best of the researchers' knowledge little or no work has been carried out on the status of tone in Yorùbá vowel coalescence. This is what the researchers aim to examine in this work.

Review of the Theoretical Framework: Auto-segmental Phonology

Auto-segmental phonology is a non-linear theory that sees tone as an independent segment that is free from modifications to segmental tiers in tonal languages. AP (henceforth) is designed by Goldsmith (1976) to cater for the limitations of generative phonology in relation to tone. Goldsmith (1976) in his work explained what AP entails when he asserts that:

A theory as auto-segmental can be judged according to three criteria: first, the theory should be able to describe any phenomenon in the language that the standard theory cannot. Second, the theory must present constraints on the acceptable representation and third, the theory must provide constraints on possible tonological rule in the language.

Other authors of AP include Clement (1989), Durand (1990), Jensen (1993), etc. Under AP the tone is seen as an independent segment. Jensen (1993) opined that:

In multi-linear representation, tones and segments are presented on a separate tier, so segments can be deleted without affecting the tone. The remaining tones are re-associated with other segments.

Oyebade (2008) explained that “non-linear phonology assumes that the features that represent each sound in an utterance are situated on different independent autonomous tiers”. The rule that guides the use of AP for language analysis is referred to as Well Formedness Condition. Durand (1990) in Oyebade (2008) explained the WFC conditions which links different independent tiers to include the following:

- i. Mapping: Associated vowels with tones in a one-to-one fashion from left to right until we run out of tones or vowels.
- ii. Dumping: If after applying (mapping) some tones are still free (that is, un-associated), link them to the last vowel to the right.
- iii. Spreading: If after applying (mapping) some vowels are still free, link them to the last tone on the right.
- iv. Association lines are not allowed to cross.

Adopted from Durand (1990).

We observed that although AP has been used by researchers in Yoruba language such as Oyebade (2001), Babarinde (1993) etc. to account for the independent status of tone in the language with evidence from phonological processes such as vowel elision, assimilation, vowel harmony and nasalization but the status of tone has not been fully established in the phonological process known as vowel coalescence especially with AP framework as analytical tool. This is what we aim to do in this work.

Tonal Stability

Tonal stability is one of the main features of Auto-segmental Phonology. It is the ability of tone to stand independently of the segmental tier (vowel and consonant).

There are three schools of thought on what Awobuluyi (1992) referred to as Coalescence by merger in the Yoruba language. The schools of thought are Fresco (1970), Stahlke (1974) and Awobuluyi (1992). Fresco (1970) explained the derivation of ‘mo’ in Yoruba language as follow:

- 2i. mi + ó
- ii. mo + ó Assimilation
- iii. mo + Ø Deletion
- iv. mo Surface form

Stahlke (1974, p. 173) has a contrary opinion to Fresco’s (1970) explanation on the derivation of ‘mo’, in the Yorùbá language, he explains that the derivation of ‘mo’ follows the following phonological process:

- 3i. mi + o
- ii. mØ + o Deletion
- iii. mo Surface form

Further-more, Awobuluyi (1992) explained coalescence by merger as a type of coalescence that occurs between segmental tier and tonal tier. He explained that in:

- 4i. mi + ó mo
- ii. wọ + ó wo

“The pronoun contributes the tonal feature, while the High Tone Syllable, henceforth (HTS) supplies the vocalic feature”. We observed that contrary to the afore-mentioned scholars’ claims, the phonological processes involved in the derivation of these words are:

- 5i. mi + ó
- ii. m – + ó Vowel elision
- iii. m + o Tonal Assimilation (the floating mid-tone assimilates the high tone of the mid high back rounded vowel /ó/.
- iv. mo Surface form.

This can be analyzed through AP thus:

In the example above, after the deletion of the high front vowel /i/. The floating mid-tone assimilates the high tone on the HTS. Goldsmith (1976) in Oyebade (2008) buttressed our claim when he asserts that:

In tone languages, we find that when a vowel dysyllabifies or is deleted by some phonological rule, the tone it was bearing does not disappear; rather it shifts its location and shows up on some other vowel.

In addition to this, Owolabi (2019) also gave credence to our assertion that tonal assimilation can occur between a mid-tone and a high tone, where the mid-tone will be the dominant tone and the high tone will be the recipient tone. Some of the examples he gave to buttress this claim include:

- | | | | |
|----------------------|---|---------|-------------------|
| 6i. Ọrún + ọrún | → | ọrọrun | ‘every five days’ |
| five days+ five days | | | |
| ii. Ọdún + ọdún | → | ọdọdun | ‘every year’ |
| year year | | | |
| iii. Alẹ + alẹ | → | alaalẹ | ‘every night’ |
| night night | | | |
| iv. isán + isán | → | isiisán | ‘every nine days’ |
| nine day nine day | | | |

From the fore-going, we observed that what Awobuluyi (1992) referred to as coalescence by merger are words that are derived through phonological processes of vowel elision and progressive tone assimilation.

Research Methodology

Being a qualitative research, this study is purely descriptive. The data for this study were purely from secondary sources elicited from existing literatures on the subject matter in Yorùbá such as, Crowther (1852), Bouche (1885), de Gaye and Beecroft (1922), Abraham (1958), Awobuluyi (1964, 1989, 1992), Oyebade (2008), Owolabi, Bamisile (1986, 1994), Babarinde (2013), Olawuwo (2021), Rabiú (2021) and so on. The intuition of the authors, being competent speakers of the language, also assisted in sourcing and validating data for the study. The data that possessed the subject of study were purposely selected for analysis within the theoretical purview of auto-segmental phonology.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Low Tone Delinking and Relinking in Yorùbá Vowel Coalescence

Low tone stability in Yoruba language has been well discussed by scholars though the tonal pattern and structure that usually trigger the delinking and relinking of the low tone in Yoruba elision have not been analyzed in Yoruba vowel coalescence. In this work, we observed that low tone stability always occurs in morphemic combination with H+ LH tonal i.e. High tone + Low tone + High tone pattern (henceforth HLH) in Yoruba vowel coalescence. Examples of HLH tonal pattern triggered low tone stability in Yoruba vowel coalescence contrary to Akinlabi's (2016) claim that this phonological process only occurs in vowel elision and assimilation are as follows:

- | | | | | | | |
|------------------|---|-----------|--------------|--------|-------|---------|
| 7i. gbó + ìró | → | gbúròó | 'hear from' | hear | sound | |
| ii. a + kí + ìṣé | → | akúṣèé' | pauper' | prefix | greet | poverty |
| iii. ogún + àrún | → | ogórùn-ún | 'hundred' | twenty | five | |
| iv. dá + ìná | → | dúnàá | 'negotiate' | utter | price | |
| v. dá + ìbú | → | dúbùú | 'lie across' | etc. | lie | bend |

In these examples, the displaced low tone of the V₂ relinks and occurs on the nearest vowel to its right and as a result renders the high tone without a tone bearing unit. The high tone spreads to the last vowel through the dumping rule of AP which states that "if after applying mapping some tones are still unassociated, then, they should be linked to the last vowel to the right as theoretically illustrated below:

Oyebade (2001, p. 152) in his work buttressed this claim about low tone stability in Yoruba language when he explained that:

The evidence for tone becomes more compelling when it is shown that in some languages; an un-arguably low-toned vowel may disappear apparently taking along with it the low tone but the impact of the low tone is still felt at the phonetic level.

This is exactly what occurs in H+ LH tonal pattern vowel coalescence, it is the same process that manifests in vowel elision that involves the same tonal pattern. We observed that H+ LH tonal pattern vowel coalescence can be referred to as non-reductive vowel coalescence since unlike none H+ LH tonal pattern vowel

coalescence where the tones and syllables always reduce after the phonological process of vowel coalescence at the surface structure level, the tones and syllables in H+ LH tonal pattern vowel coalescence always remain the same at the surface structure level.

Tonal Assimilation

Assimilation has been defined as the changing of a segment totally or partially by a contiguous or non-contiguous segment. Tone assimilation on the other hand is the ability of neighbouring tones to totally change the tone before or after it. We observed that tone sometimes in the process of vowel coalescence assimilates rather than coalescing together. For example:

- 8i. dá + ọpé → dúpé ‘give thanks’ give thanks
- ii. abé + ilé → abúlé ‘village’ under house
- iii. a rí + ogbó → arúgbó ‘old man/woman’
prefix see old
- iv. ì + wí + oyè → iwúyè ‘coronation’ prefix say
chieftaincy
- 9i. ogún + èjì → ogójì ‘forty’ twenty two
- ii. ogún + èta → ogóta ‘sixty’ twenty three
- iii. ogún + èrin → ogórin ‘eighty’ twenty four
- iv. jẹ́ + ibà → júbà ‘pay homage’ answer
homage
- v. ìṣe + kí + ìṣe → ìṣekúṣe ‘bad habit’ habit bad habit
- vi. ìjẹ́ + kí + ìjẹ́ → ìjẹ́kújẹ́ ‘bad eating’ etc. food bad
food
- vii. ì + wí + ìre → iwúre ‘prayer’ prefix say
prayer
- viii. à + wí + ìre → àwúre ‘fortune’ prefix say
prayer
- 10i. ò mọ́ iwẹ́ → òmùwẹ́ ‘swimmer’ prefix know
swim
- ii. jọ́ + ìmọ́ → jùmọ́ ‘agreed’ together know

Tonal Coalescence

Coalescence is a phonological process that occurs when two contrasting segments merge together to form a new segment. Oyebade (2008) explained that “when two contiguous segments at the underlying representation disappear at the surface phonetic level to be replaced by a third segment which shares features from both of the segments that disappeared, it is said that they have coalesced into one”. Bamgbose (1990) propound this formula for vowel coalescence:

$$V_1 + V_2 \longrightarrow V_3$$

Tone coalescence on the other hand is the fusion of two independent register tones at the underlying level to a new tone that is different from the two coalesced tones at the surface level. Following Bamgbose (1990) schema for vowel coalescence, tonal coalescence can be represented as shown in the schema below:

$$T_1 + T_2 \longrightarrow T_3$$

Tonal coalescence in the Yorùbá language is not as pronounced as vowel coalescence. Ajiboye (2020) gave credence to this assertion when he opined that “Coalescence, of tone to the best of my knowledge, has not been reported in the literature. The closest one known to me is tone simplification (Abiodun and Ajiboye, 2008). Ajiboye (2020) in his work on Mòbà dialect explained that “In Mòbà dialect, I opine that there is coalescence of high tone and a low tone to a mid-tone in certain syntactic contexts”. He gave the following examples to buttress his claim:

- | | | | |
|--------------|--------|---------|-------------------|
| 12i. dé òkó | —————> | dokó | ‘reach Òkò’ |
| ii. wá èbùn | —————> | wẹ̀bùn | ‘search for Èbùn’ |
| iii. rí ọ̀nà | —————> | rọ̀nà | ‘see pathway’ |
| iv. gbé èkó | —————> | gbekòò | ‘live in Lagos’ |
| v. kọ̀ èkọ̀ | —————> | kẹ̀kọ̀ó | ‘learn lesson’ |

Prepositional Phrase

- | | | | | |
|---------|--------|--------|---------|-------------|
| 13i. ní | ùwó | —————> | luwòó | ‘at Iwo’ |
| ii. ní | ẹ̀gbá | —————> | lẹ̀gbàá | ‘at Ègba’ |
| iii. sí | ìlàwẹ̀ | —————> | silawẹ̀ | ‘at ilawẹ̀’ |
| iv. sí | ọ̀wọ̀ | —————> | sọ̀wò | ‘at Ọ̀wọ̀’ |

Ajiboye (2020)

Few evidence of tonal coalescence that has been discovered by these researchers can be classified into two, which are simultaneous vowel and tone coalescence and

independent tone coalescence that usually occur after the phonological process of vowel elision in Yoruba language.

Simultaneous Tone and Vowel Coalescence

These researchers observed that tone and vowel coalescence sometimes occur simultaneously at the same time in the Yorùbá language. Example of such dual coalescence process in Yoruba language includes:

12i. orí + ilé → òrùlé ‘rooftop’ head house

The phonological processes that occur in the derivation of this word at the phonetic level can be represented as follow:

ii. orí + ilé

òrùlé (vowel and tonal coalescence occur simultaneously)

Vowel /i/ with a high tone which is the V^1 coalesced with the vowel /i/ with a mid-tone which is the V^2 to form the output vowel /u/ which is the V^3 . Also, the high tone of the high front vowel in “orí” ‘head’ which is the T_1 coalesced with the mid-tone of the high front vowel /i/ in “ilé” which is the T_2 to form the output low tone on the coalesced /ù/ that is the T_3 .

iii. òrùlé (regressive non-contiguous tonal assimilation occurs between the low tone on vowel /u/ and the mid-tone on vowel /o/ to form “òrùlé” ‘top of the roof’.

iv. òrùlé ‘rooftop’

Independent Tone Coalescence

This is the type of tone coalescence that occurs after the elision of one of the two contiguous vowels at morpheme boundary. Examples of independent tone coalescence in the Yorùbá language include:

13i. èrò + kí + èrò → èròkerò ‘bad thought’ thought bad thought

In this example, the high tone of the elided high front vowel /i/ of the affix “kí” ‘bad’ which is the T_1 coalesced with the low tone on the rightward “èrò” ‘thought’ which is the T_2 to form the new output mid-tone which is the T_3 . The phonological processes that occur in the derivation of this word at the phonetic level can be represented as follow:

ii. èrò + kí + èrò

iii. èrò + k’ + èrò – Deletion of vowel /i/ with the retainment of its high tone.

iv. èrò + k + erò- The floating high tone of the deleted vowel /i/ coalesced with the low tone of vowel /è/ to form a new output mid-tone

v. èròkerò - Surface form

ii. ọ̀ + jẹ + ọ̀gbọ̀n → ọ̀jọ̀gbọ̀n ‘professor’ prefix eat wisdom

Unlike tone deletion that usually occurs when two mid-tones occur contiguously in vowel coalescence, we observed that the occurrence of two mid-tones in example (14) triggered what is referred to as tonal coalescence rather than deletion. In the derivation of this word, the following phonological processes occur:

i. ọ̀ j ọ̀gbọ̀n – Deletion of the vowel /ɛ/ in “jẹ” ‘eat’ and the retainment of the mid-tone on it.

ii. ọ̀jọ̀gbọ̀n- The two mid-tones, that is, the floating mid-tone of the deleted vowel and the mid-tone on vowel /ɔ/ in “ọ̀gbọ̀n” coalesced together to form a low tone as the output tone. The floating mid tone is T₁, the mid-tone of the noun “ọ̀gbọ̀n” ‘wisdom is the T₂ while the derived low tone is the T₃.

Ọ̀jọ̀gbọ̀n ‘professor’ Surface form’

Other examples of independent tone coalescence can be found in Yoruba numerals that are used for the counting of days backward in the Yorùbá language. Examples of such include:

14i. ọ̀jọ̀ + ẹ̀ta	→	ọ̀jẹ̀ta	‘three days ago’	day	three
ii. ọ̀jọ̀ + ẹ̀rin	→	ọ̀jẹ̀rin	‘four days ago’	day	four
iii. ọ̀jọ̀ + àrún	→	ọ̀jẹ̀rún-ún	‘five days ago’	day	five
iv. ọ̀jọ̀ + ẹ̀fà	→	‘ọ̀jẹ̀fà	‘six days ago’	day	six
v. ọ̀jọ̀ + ẹ̀je	→	‘ọ̀jẹ̀je	‘seven days ago’	day	seven
vi. ọ̀jọ̀ + ẹ̀jọ̀	→	ọ̀jẹ̀jọ̀	‘eight days ago’	day	eight
vii. ọ̀jọ̀ + ẹ̀sán	→	‘ọ̀jẹ̀sán-án	‘nine days ago’	day	nine
viii. ọ̀jọ̀ + ẹ̀wá	→	ọ̀jẹ̀wáá	‘ten days ago’	day	ten

In examples (14i-viii), the researchers observed that tone coalescence occur between the floating high tone of the elided vowel /ɔ/ in “ọ̀jọ̀” ‘day and the low tone on the first syllable and vowel of the numerals which are /ɛ, e and a/ respectively to form mid-tone on the surviving vowels at the surface level.

Summary of Findings

- i. In the prosodic analysis of vowel coalescence in Yorùbá, we observed that the phonological process of Yorùbá, tone undergoes the following: assimilation, deletion, tone delinking and relinking and tone coalescence.

- ii. On the distribution of tone in these processes, we observed what we referred to as high tonal superiority under our tone assimilation in that, high tone assimilates mid and low tone, while low tone also assimilates mid tone.

$$T_1 + T_2 \rightarrow T_1 / T_2$$

On the tonal deletion, such superiority is suspended in such a way that the input tones and the output tone are similar. That is, high versus high will generate high, low versus low will generate low, and low versus low will generate, though low + low will generate low tone with the exception of example (14) where low + low generate tone coalescence rather than tone deletion.

$$T_1 + T \rightarrow T_1 \& T_2$$

For tone coalescence, the input and the output tones are distinct. The T_3 is distinct from the T_1 and T_2 .

$$T_1 + T_2 \rightarrow T_3$$

- iii. Based on the stability of tone in Yorùba vowel coalescence, vowel coalescence in the Yorùbá language can be classified into reductive and non-reductive vowel coalescence. By reductive we mean that the number of syllables at the surface structure would reduce after the process of vowel coalescence while in non-reductive vowel coalescence the number of syllables would be the same, that is, it would not reduce at the surface structure level after vowel coalescence has taken place.
- iv. It was also discovered that Oyebade (2008, p. 182) claims that a displaced low tone introduces a contour tone with a following high tone contrast evidence from Yoruba vowel coalescence and elision which show that displaced low tone only introduces a contour tone whenever it precedes and follows high tones, that is, when it is in between two high tones (HLH).
- v. Lastly, one of the major strength of this study is the observation and validation of the fact that just as we have vowel coalescence in Yoruba, there is also the presence of tonal coalescence in the Yoruba language.

Conclusion

It is apparent from our prosodic analysis of the phonological process of vowel coalescence in the Yorùbá language that tone plays a significant role in the realisation of phonological processes in Yoruba, vowel coalescence inclusive. This, we believe is not limited to Yorùbá but may likely be traced to other tonal languages. Its phonemicity determines what is omitted or retained at different syllabic boundaries in the distribution of the processes. The significance of tone helps in attempting a generalisation based on the formation observed so far.

REFERENCES

- Abraham, R.C. (1958). *Dictionary of Modern Yoruba*. London: University of London Press Ltd.
- Ajiboye, O. (2020). *Demystifying Optimality Theory: A Pedagogical Approach*. Lagos: Kingdom Arts Publishing
- Awobuluyi, O. (1984). Towards a Typology Coalescence. In *Journal of West African Languages*.
- Awóbùlúyì, O. (1992). "Aspects of Contemporary Standard Yorùbá in Dialectological Perspectives" in Ìṣòlá, A. (Ed.) *J.F. Odúnjò Memorial Lecture 3: New Findings in Yorùbá Studies*. Department of Linguistics and African Languages.
- Babarinde, O. (2013). The Linguistics Analysis of the Structure of the Yorùbá Numerals. *Journal of Literature, Language and Linguistics*.
- Bámgbòsé, A. (1990). *Fonólójì àti Gírámà Yorùba*. Ibadan: University Press Plc.
- Bamisile, R. (1994). Justification for the Survival of Vowel Coalescence as a Phonological Process in Yorùbá. *Journal of African Languages and Cultures*. Vol.7, No2.
- Crowther, S. (1852). *A Grammar of the Yoruba Language*. London: Seeley's
- Durand, J. (1990). *Generative and Non-Linear Phonology*. New York: Longman
- Fadairo, O.A. (2014). Phonological Processes in Yorùbá: A Complementarity Approach. *Ihafa Journal of African Studies*. Vol.6 No1.
- Goldsmith, J. (1976). *Autosegmental Phonology*. Indiana: Indiana University Linguistic Club
- Olawuwo, T. (2021). Divergence Opinion on Coalescence in Yoruba. *International Journal of Contemporary Education Research*, Published by Cambridge Research and Publications IJ CER ISSN-2891-5226 (Print) 105 Vol. 22 No. 8.
- Owólabí, K. (2019). *Ìjìnlẹ̀ Ìtupalẹ̀ Èdè Yorùbá Fónétìkì àti Fonólójì*. Ibadan: Positive Press
- Oyèbádé, F. (2001). *Ìgbésẹ̀ àti Ìlànà Fonólójì Èdè Yorùbá nínú Àjàyí B (Olóòtú) Èkó Ìjìnlẹ̀ Yorùbá: Èdà-Èdè, Litírẹ̀ṣọ̀ àti Àṣà*. Ìjẹ̀bú-Òde: Sebiotimo Publication
- Oyèbádé, F. (2008). *A Course in Phonology*. Ìjẹ̀bú-Òde: Sebiotimo Publications.

Rabiu, R.A. (2021) Àtúngbéyèwò Ìgbésè Ìyópò Fáwèlì Nínú Èdè Yorùbá: Èrí Láti Inú Orúkọ A Ajemọ Ibi àti Ẹni. K.A. Rafiu (Ed.) *Ilorin Journal of Linguistics, Literature and Culture. Vol 10*. Ilorin: Department of Linguistics and Nigerian Languages, University of Ilorin, Ilorin.